

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF DEGRADATION PROCESSES IN LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A continuum damage theory for brittle deformation processes in laminated fiber-reinforced composites is presented. Three mutually orthogonal damage modes are distinguished, which are associated with matrix cracking, fiber breaks and delaminations. These damage modes are characterized by a symmetric second order tensor. The governing equations are solved by employing the finite element method. The continuous deterioration of laminate structures under quasistatic loading is investigated. Special attention is given to the mesh objectivity of the numerical simulations. A comparison of results against experimental data shows good agreement.

Keywords: damage mechanics, laminated composites, finite element analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

A rational approach for dealing with problems characterized by the dominant role of microcracking in energy dissipation is provided by Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) [1]. In CDM the irreversible changes are characterized locally by an internal variable, which reflects the effects of microcracking. Thus, the damage variable can be understood to be a measure of the microcrack density and distribution. On the macroscale, relationships between material response characteristics and the internal variable are formulated. The evolution of the internal variable through the loading process results in a continuous deterioration of the material stiffness. In this paper a continuum damage theory for brittle deformation processes in laminated fiber-reinforced composites is presented. The term "brittle" signifies that the loss of integrity, characterized by the microcrack density and distribution, is the major source of energy dissipation. In laminated fiber-reinforced composites three mutually orthogonal damage modes can be distinguished: transverse matrix cracks, fiber breaks and local delaminations. These damage modes are characterized by a symmetric second order tensor. The damage formulation is discussed in detail in [2]. The complete damage model requires: (1) the assessment of a stress strain relation for damaged materials, (2) a damage growth law, and (3) a criterion for damage growth. The model has been implemented in the DIANA finite element package. Detailed information on the numerical procedures is provided in [3]. The response of laminate structures to quasistatic loadings is investigated. The influence of mesh refinement on the finite element analyses is discussed. The

application of localization limiters to avoid the occurrence of spurious solutions is briefly adressed.

2. CONSTITUTIVE THEORY

During an irreversible thermodynamic process, the elastic strain and stress are insufficient to describe the state of the material locally. The changes in the microstructure must be defined by an additional set of internal variables. It is assumed that microcrack nucleation and growth is the dominant mode of microstructural changes. Then an internal variable \mathbf{D} characterizing the damage must be introduced. In what follows we restrict ourselves to linear elastic materials under isothermal conditions. For all admissible past histories of the state variables the constitutive laws must satisfy the Clausius-Duhem inequality. Application of the Clausius-Duhem inequality implies that the stress-strain relation can be written as [2]

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = {}^4\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{D}) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

In addition, the damage rate tensor must obey

$$\mathbf{X} : \dot{\mathbf{D}} \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{X} is the thermodynamic force conjugate to the thermodynamic flux $\dot{\mathbf{D}}$

$$\mathbf{X} = -\frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \frac{\partial {}^4\mathbf{C}}{\partial \mathbf{D}} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

The thermodynamic force can alternatively be written in a stress-based form

$$\mathbf{X} = \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \frac{\partial {}^4\mathbf{S}}{\partial \mathbf{D}} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (4)$$

with ${}^4\mathbf{S}$ the compliance tensor.

A criterion for damage growth is established by proposing the existence of a closed domain Ω in the thermodynamic force space, which contains the origin and which is bounded by the surface Γ . The damage surface is a piecewise smooth and convex surface enveloping the locus of all points in the space of thermodynamic forces which can be reached without change in the current state. Let the damage kinetics be governed by m active modes, where each mode refers to an ensemble of cracks with (initially) identical geometrical features. Then the reversible domain Ω is formally expressed as

$$\Omega = \bigcap_{\alpha=1}^m \Omega_{\alpha} \quad ; \quad \Omega_{\alpha} = \{ \mathbf{X} \mid \phi_{\alpha}(\mathbf{X}, v_{\alpha}) < 0 \} \quad (5)$$

where v_{α} is a history dependent parameter, which defines the current location of the damage surface for mode α in the space of thermodynamic forces.

To describe the propagation of damage the existence of a convex, semi-continuous dissipation potential function in the space of thermodynamic forces with a minimum 0 for $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{0}$ is postulated. Analogous to the theory of associated plasticity this dissipation potential is identified with ϕ_{α} . Invoking the normality rule the rate of change of the damage for mode α is defined as

$$\dot{\mathbf{D}}^{(\alpha)} = \lambda_{\alpha} \frac{\partial \phi_{\alpha}}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \quad (6)$$

$$\lambda_\alpha = \dot{v}_\alpha \quad (7)$$

with λ_α a nonnegative multiplier. It can be verified easily that (6) satisfies the Clausius-Duhem inequality for convex ϕ_α . The conditions for damage growth are formulated as

$$\phi_\alpha \leq 0 ; \lambda_\alpha \geq 0 ; \lambda_\alpha \phi_\alpha = 0 \quad (8)$$

In other words if $\phi_\alpha < 0$ the damage multiplier must be zero and there is no damage growth. In case of damage growth we must have that $\phi_\alpha = 0$. Then the damage multiplier follows from the consistency condition

$$\dot{\phi}_\alpha = 0 \Rightarrow \dot{v}_\alpha = - \left(\frac{\partial \phi_\alpha}{\partial v_\alpha} \right)^{-1} \left\langle \frac{\partial \phi_\alpha}{\partial \mathbf{X}} : \dot{\mathbf{X}} \right\rangle \quad (9)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the McAuley brackets.

3. COMPOSITE LAMINATES

3.1 Stress-strain relation

In the progressive failure of uni-directionally reinforced composite laminates, it is assumed that the defect directions coincide with the mutually orthogonal axes of symmetry $\vec{n}_1, \vec{n}_2, \vec{n}_3$, with the subscripts 1, 2 and 3 designating the fiber direction, the transverse direction and the normal direction in a laminate ply. Then the damage tensor takes the form

$$\mathbf{D} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^3 \mathbf{D}^{(\alpha)} ; \mathbf{D}^{(\alpha)} = D_\alpha \vec{n}_\alpha \otimes \vec{n}_\alpha \quad (10)$$

with $\alpha = 1, 2, 3$ denoting fiber fracture, matrix cracking and delamination respectively. In what follows we restrict attention to fiber fracture and transverse matrix cracking.

The stress-strain relation is influenced by the existence of transverse matrix cracks and fiber breaks. The effects of regular arrays of transverse matrix cracks on the stress-strain behavior have been established by Laws et al. [4], who employed a self consistent method. This approach was used by Paas and van den Eikhoff [3] to calculate the compliances S_{22} and S_{66} for varying matrix crack densities. For computational convenience the compliances were fitted by exponential functions. The effects of fiber fracture are accounted for by assuming that S_{11} and S_{66} are inversely proportional to the density of broken fibers ($0 \leq D_1 < 1$). Hence, the damage induced compliances for a unidirectional reinforced ply are approximated as

$$[S] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{11}^0(1-D_1)} & -\frac{v_{12}^0}{E_{11}} & 0 \\ -\frac{v_{12}^0}{E_{11}} & \frac{\exp(\gamma_{22}D_2)}{E_{22}^0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\exp(\gamma_{66}D_2)}{2G_{12}^0(1-kD_1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where k is a positive constant, γ_{22} and γ_{66} are best-fit coefficients in the exponential fit functions.

3.2 Damage evolution

Because the defect directions are channeled by the presence of fibers and adjacent plies, the initial symmetry is recovered for all damage states. The requirement that the initial defect directions do not change, necessarily involves that the dissipation potential ϕ_α may only depend on X_α . Under this restriction the evolution law becomes

$$\dot{D} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^3 \dot{D}^{(\alpha)} ; \quad \dot{D}^{(\alpha)} = \lambda_\alpha \frac{\partial \phi_\alpha}{\partial X_\alpha} \vec{n}_\alpha \otimes \vec{n}_\alpha \quad (\text{no sum on } \alpha) \quad (12)$$

It is remarked that the damage formulation in [2] is suitable for large displacement analysis.

Using (4) and (11) the thermodynamic force associated with fiber fracture is

$$X_1 = \frac{1}{(1-D_1)^2} \frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{2E_{11}^0} + \frac{k \exp(\gamma_{66} D_2)}{(1-kD_1)^2} \frac{\sigma_{21}^2}{4G_{12}^0} \quad (13)$$

and the thermodynamic force associated with transverse matrix cracking is

$$X_2 = \exp(\gamma_{22} D_2) \frac{\gamma_{22} (\sigma_{22})^2}{2E_{22}^0} + \exp(\gamma_{66} D_2) \frac{\gamma_{66} \sigma_{21}^2}{4G_{12}^0} \quad (14)$$

Damage growth in mode α occurs when the associated thermodynamic forces exceed a critical value. This can be warranted by choosing the dissipation potential as a linear function of the thermodynamic forces

$$\phi_\alpha = A_\alpha [X_\alpha - \nu_\alpha X_\alpha^0] \quad (15)$$

with A_α a positive constant. Combining (13) and (14) it follows that $\phi_\alpha = 0$ is an ellipse in stress space. Using (15) and (12) the damage evolution law can be integrated as

$$D_\alpha = D_\alpha^0 + A_\alpha (\nu_\alpha - 1) ; \quad \nu_\alpha = \max_{0 < \tau < t} \left[1, \frac{X_\alpha(\tau)}{X_\alpha^0} \right] \quad (16)$$

4. RESULTS

Since dissipative mechanisms take place, a particular analysis includes history dependent phenomena. The loading history is applied in increments. In each loading increment the displacement field and the damage must be determined. The model is implemented in the DIANA finite element package. The numerical procedures involved were discussed in [3]. Emphasis was placed on the derivation of the linearized finite element equations, the determination of the damage, the damage surface, the tangential stiffness matrix and the application of arc-length control to pass the limit point in the load-displacement curves. Next some example applications are presented, showing the response of damaging laminates to monotonic loadings.

4.1 Uniaxial loading

Consider uniaxial loading of a graphite-epoxy AS4/3501-6 [0/90₂]_s laminate. The stress state in the plies is assumed to be homogeneous. A simplified one-dimensional analysis is carried out together with a finite element analysis. The material data are given in Table 1. The strain at which damage

growth in the 90° layer starts is $\epsilon_0 = Y/E_T^0$ with Y the transverse tensile strength. It is assumed that damage propagation in the fiber mode is revealed as instantaneous laminate failure ($A_1 \gg 1$). The associated strain is $\epsilon_c = X/E_L^0$ with X the tensile strength. Using $A_2 = 1$, the maximum recorded transverse stress in the 90° layer can be derived as [2]

$$\sigma_{22} = Y \sqrt{(D_2 + 1) \exp(-\gamma_{22} D_2)} \tag{17}$$

Figure 1. Stress-strain relation for 90° ply in $[0/90_2]_s$ AS4/3501-6 laminate; --- analytical solution and — numerical solution.

Figure 2. Global stress versus D_2 for $[0/90_2]_s$ AS4/3501-6 laminate.

Figure 1 shows the stress-strain relation for the 90° ply. After the threshold ϵ_0 is exceeded, softening occurs. Figure 2 shows the global stress versus D_2 according to the analytical solution and the finite element analysis. The finite element predictions and the analytical predictions almost coincide. The experimental results obtained by Lee and Daniel [5] are also shown. Close agreement between experimental and calculated results is observed.

E_L [MPa]	E_T [MPa]	G_{LT} [MPa]	ν_{LT} [-]	Y [MPa]	X [MPa]	γ_{22} [-]	γ_{66} [-]
142000	10300	7600	0.3	51.7	1447	1.93	0.77

Table 1 Material Parameters for graphite-epoxy AS4/3501-6 [5].

4.2 Bending

Consider a $[0/90_2]_s$ AS4/3501-6 graphite-epoxy laminated structure with dimensions $20 \times 2 \times 0.75 \text{ mm}^3$. The structure is loaded at the right end by a vertical force F . The finite element discretization is shown in Figure 3. The material data are given in Table 1. The load-deflection curve is presented in Figure 4. Some characteristic events in the failure process are marked A, B, C, D. At point A transverse cracks initiate in the 90° plies in the upper left element. A slight deflection of the slope of the stress-strain curve can be observed between A and B. At point B fiber fracture initiates in the upper left element. This event has significant influence on the stress-strain curve. At C a limit point is encountered. Beyond C softening occurs leading to rapid structural failure at point D.

Figure 3. Structure subjected to monotonic static loading.

Figure 4 Force vs. end displacement of $[0/90_2]_s$ AS4/3501-6 laminate.

4.3 Mesh sensitivity

Structural softening is a phenomenon which is observed in the damaging of heterogeneous materials [6]. After the limit point (point C in Figure 4), where the damage becomes more localized, numerous different solutions can occur depending on the local mesh size. Structural softening and the resulting mesh sensitivity is also observed for composite structures [7]. In [3] the mesh-sensitivity of the numerical simulations was investigated by comparing the solutions obtained for mesh refinement. This was done in both horizontal and vertical directions. No mesh dependence was observed upon mesh-refinement in the vertical direction. Mesh refinement in the horizontal direction led to spurious solutions converging to a zero energy dissipation solution for vanishing mesh size, which is a physically unacceptable solution. The anisotropy in mesh sensitivity is caused by the anisotropy in the damage, where fiber breaks dictate the softening behavior. To remedy this situation a localization limiter must be introduced, which prevents the structure from localization in an infinitely small region. Several approaches can be found in literature, such as gradient dependent models, nonlocal damage models and rate dependent models [8]. Recently, Paas and Van den Eikhoff [9] showed that the application of a local damage parameter in conjunction with a characteristic length scale does reduce the mesh sensitivity and prevents the structure from failure with zero energy dissipation. The effects of mesh refinement on the response of the structure of Figure 3 were assessed. Because structural softening is governed by fiber breaks, the analyses were carried out for one uni-directional ply only. The results of a linear softening model with a characteristic length scale of one quarter of the structure are shown in Figure 5. From these results it follows that the mesh dependence is greatly reduced by the introduction of the localization parameter (characteristic length).

Figure 5. Load vs. end displacement for mesh refinement in horizontal direction.

5. DISCUSSION

An anisotropic damage theory was presented for composite materials subjected to quasistatic loadings. The theory was developed on a thermodynamical basis. Microcracking was considered to be the only dissipative mechanism. The constitutive equations were partly inspired by micromechanics. The stress-strain relation was determined with a self consistent method, the criterion for damage growth and the evolution law were inspired by fracture mechanics. The progressive failure of laminate structures subjected to quasistatic loading was studied. In [2] the response of structures subjected to fatigue loading is discussed as well. For the uniaxial load case good correspondence with available experimental data was obtained.

The mesh sensitivity which is a major problem in dealing with softening materials was addressed. Unless some form of localization limiter is introduced, physically meaningless solutions may be obtained. Especially in case of impact loading of laminates leading to local delaminations, experiments may reveal significant softening. Future work will be directed toward the modeling of delaminations in connection with the mesh sensitivity of the numerical simulations.

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